

Study of Fluoride Adsorption of Kota Stone Slurry on Different Parameter of Surface Area and Effect of Fluoride Adsorption on KSS by XRD Study

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ABSTRACT:

Kota the city of Rajasthan, known as a city of education and city of stone. Mostly mining areas are present in Hadoti region, Suket, Morak, Ramganjmandietc in Kota. Kota called city of stone due to large mining and polishing factories developed in these areas. These stone industries generated large amount of stone waste and slurry waste. Which is major environmental problem and hazardous factor for different aspects of land, air, water and humans. The present study concludes that Kota Stone Slurry effectively use as allowed cost material for removal fluoride. Fluoride in water is also environmental problem in this area due to land nature, ground water has high concentration of fluoride above 5ppm. which is harmful for health purpose. KSS is good adsorbent for fluoride. Our previous study shows that KSS can use as fluoride adsorbent, it gives good adsorption approx 70 to 80 percent, due to its chemical composition. After fluoride adsorption KSS show changes in physical or chemical properties. So in this paper focused on fluoride adsorption on KSS on different parameter of surface areas and XRD and SEM study before and after fluoride adsorption.

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I INTRODUCTION

In recent years, concerns over water quality and environmental health have heightened global attention towards the presence of fluoride in water sources. High levels of fluoride in

drinking water pose significant health risks, including dental and skeletal fluorosis, especially in regions where natural fluoride concentrations exceed permissible limits. Various techniques have been developed to mitigate fluoride contamination, among which adsorption using locally available materials stands out as a promising and cost-effective solution. Kota Stone, a widely used building material known for its durability and abundance, has garnered attention for its potential in fluoride adsorption. Kota Stone Slurry (KSS), a byproduct of the stone processing industry, exhibits properties conducive to fluoride adsorption owing to its high surface area and porous structure. Understanding the adsorption behavior of KSS and its interaction with fluoride ions is crucial for developing efficient water treatment strategies.

This study focuses on investigating the fluoride adsorption capacity of Kota Stone Slurry under different surface area parameters. By manipulating surface area characteristics through various treatments, including physical and chemical modifications, we aim to elucidate the influence of surface properties on fluoride adsorption efficiency. Additionally, employing X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis allows for a comprehensive examination of structural changes in KSS upon fluoride adsorption, providing insights into the underlying mechanisms governing the adsorption process. Through systematic experimentation and analysis, this study endeavors to contribute to the growing body of knowledge surrounding fluoride removal using locally available materials. By elucidating the relationship between surface area parameters, fluoride adsorption capacity, and structural alterations in KSS, we aspire to provide valuable insights for the development of sustainable and effective water treatment solutions, particularly in regions grappling with fluoride contamination issues.

II LITERATURE REVIEW

Kota is located on Hadoti region, eastern south part of Rajasthan. its land nature is major source of and reserve of dimensional stone Kota stone and lime stone etc. also available in different varieties and texture [1]. Kota has large market and many mining and polishing industries [2]. It provides self-business and employment and increase comfort of human life but in other hand it is responsible for many hazardous problem and environmental problem. it pollutes the air, water, land and human's activities and health [3,4]. The stone industry generates an extremely large number of wastes from mined areas in the form of mine wastes to processing and polishing wastes at gang saws locations. Natural and artificial stone industry generates large volume of stone waste [5]. It is in various forms such as powder or fines, aggregates, larger stone pieces and cobbles, damaged blocks or slabs and stone slurry [6-10].

By the mining industry has quality of groundwater resources disturbed in the State of Rajasthan and these industries are becoming centres of pollution sources which need timely actions at government level so that natural resources such as groundwater can be protected [11]. Stone industry generates both solid waste and stone slurry. Where solid waste

results from the rejects at the mine sites or at the processing units, stone slurry is a semi liquid substance consisting of particles originating from the sawing and the polishing processes and water used to cool and lubricate the sawing and polishing machines [12, 13]. Stone waste generated during processing corresponds to around 40% of the final product from stone industry. Presence of abnormally high F concentration in groundwater's in Kota districts of Rajasthan [14]. It is second most environmental problem of ground water it is not due to anthropogenic reasons. It is due to natural cause of higher abundance of F-bearing minerals in the host rocks and sediments [15]. The important rocks are limestone, sandstone, phosphoresce, shale's, clays, acid igneous rocks, basalts, alluvium, etc [16]. and these obtain floristic minerals accounting for F in the range 5 to 10 ppm (average). Their chemical behaviour like decomposition, dissociation, dissolution and interaction with water is considered to be the main cause of F in groundwater [17].

Distribution of F is also related to regional hydro geological and climatic condition. Besides the hydro geological set-up, climate and physiographic are other important factors[18,19]. The areas of less rainfall have waters with higher F content compared to groundwater in high rainfall areas, despite similar hydro geological formation[20,21].kota area are included according to rain fall above average rain fall dilution along with rapid flushing out of salts in high rainfall and hilly areas result in low F content in waters of these areas[22]. The weathering and leaching process, mainly by moving and percolating water, also plays an important role in reducing or increasing of F concentration in groundwater. Other factors like chemical composition, presence and accessibility of F minerals to water and contact time between the source of minerals and water also govern the release of F into water [23,24]. The high concentration of fluoride is the most affected with dental, skeletal and/or non skeletal fluorosis[25]. Membrane technique is a low cost and easy technique which may be used in the treatment for fluoride removal. Removal of fluoride by activated alumina is an established treatment technology[26].

III METHODOLOGY

Environmental Problems of KSS And Fluoride

Table 1.1:Concentration of Fluoride their Effect[27-30].

S.N.	Fluoride in Drinking Water	Effect
1.	0.002 mg/l in air	Injury to vegetation
2.	1mg/l in water	Dental caries reduction
3.	2 mg/l in water	Mottled enamel
4.	3.1-6.0 mg/l in water	Osteoporosis
5.	8 mg/l in water	10 % Osteoporosis
6.	20-80 mg/day or more in water or air	Crippling skeletal fluorosis

7.	50mg/l in water or food	Thyroid change
8.	100 mg/l in water or food	Growth retardation
9.	More than 125mg/l in water	Kidney change
10.	2.5-5.0 gm in actual dose	Death

Harmful Effect of Kota Stone Slurry

Kota Stone Slurry, a hazardous-stone slurry is a semi-liquid substance consisting of particles originated from the sawing and polishing processes and water used to cool and lubricate the sawing and polishing machines[31,32]. The main problems caused by this waste area. Some of the ill effects of stone dust wastes are given as under –

- The stone waste is indestructible
- Dumping grounds gives repulsive dirty looks
- Land fertility of agricultural land is totally impaired
- Loss of valuable top soil is due to blanketing with dust
- Contamination of reverse nulls and other surface water bodies[33]
- Slurry affects productivity of land due to decreased porosity water absorption and percolation
- Slurry dumped areas can't support vegetation
- The fine particles of slurry get entrenched into land [34]
- capillaries and block ground aquifers recharging
- Drains and nallas are choked due to settling of fine dust and adjoining agricultural fields are flooded with rain water, making crops losses.
- Dust nuisance
- Fine particles of slurry(size less than 363micron) become airborne and cause air pollution [35]
- Public outcry against the dust nuisance

Kota stone slurry chemical composition-

Table 1.2: Chemical Composition of Kota Stone Slurry Waste by XRF Technique.

S.N.	Chemical Properties	Kota stone Slurry
1	Calcium Oxide (CaO)	37.3%
2	Silica (SiO ₂)	24.9 %
3	Aluminum Trioxide(Al ₂ O ₃)	1.37 %
4	Potassium Oxide K ₂ O	0.4 %
5	Magnesium Oxide (MgO)	4.13 %
6	Loss on ignition (LOI) (%)	32.94 %
7	Ferrous Oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	0.86 %
8	Sodium Oxide Na ₂ O	1.21 %
9	Titanium oxide	0.05%

The Kota stone slurry is found to contain Calcium, Potassium and Magnesium as macronutrients and iron, copper manganese zinc etc. as micronutrients. Some ultra-micronutrients are also found in the waste -Titanium, Vanadium, Copper, Zinc, Manganese, rubidium and strontium[37-40].

Kota stone slurry(KSS) chemical composition shows that batter percentage of calcium, aluminum, iron, and magnesium. which is a good indication of removal of fluoride by KSS through the adsorption method[41].

IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Adsorption Of Fluoride Effected By Surface Area of KSS

Variation of Particle Size for adsorption of fluoride

Particle size of KSS has a significant effect on Fluoride adsorption. The effect of variation of particle size was studied on KSS (Kota Stone Slurry).In fact; particle size is an important parameter to study the adsorption of toxic metals and pollutants onto different adsorbents[42,43].

The reduction in Fluoride adsorption capacity with increase in KSS samples size gives an idea about the porosity of adsorbent i.e., if the adsorbent is highly porous then it would not have significant effect on Fluoride adsorption at equilibrium[44,45]. The results obtained are in accordance with adsorption, where smaller particles of adsorbents the rate of fluoride uptake. The similar results were obtained in previous studies[46-50].

Table 1.3: Percentage variation in concentration of Fluoride with different particle sizes (300 BSS, 200 BSS and 100 BSS) of KSS.

% Variation in Fluoride concentration with different particle sizes of KSS			
Concentration	100 BSS	200 BSS	300 BSS
2 mg/l	75.00	80.00	95.00
4 mg/l	70.00	75.00	92.50
6 mg/l	66.67	71.67	86.67
8 mg/l	58.75	60.00	66.25
10 mg/l	40.00	46.00	52.00

Fluoride adsorption as compared to the smaller particle size of KSS samples.

It is due basic theory of surface phenomena. If surface area increases due to decrease particle size than adsorption of fluoride also increases. Surface area inversely proportional to particle size and adsorption is directly proportional to surface area. KSS particle size has a significant influence on Fluoride adsorption from aqueous solutions because of different distribution of active centres on the heterogeneous KSS samples.

It is clear from results that amount of Fluoride adsorption increases on decreasing particle size from 100,200 and 300 BSS mesh (**Figure 1.1 to 1.2**). The relatively higher adsorption with smaller KSS particles is attributed to the fact that smaller particles yield large surface areas for adsorption of Fluoride. The larger particle size of KSS samples shows lesser

Fig 1.1:Variation in adsorption of fluoride concentration by different particle sizes (300 BSS, 200 BSS and 100 BSS) of Kota Stone Slurry (KSS).

Fig. 1.2: Variation in fluoride concentration by different particle sizes (300 BSS, 200 BSS and 100 BSS) of Kota Stone Slurry (KSS).

The reason is that surface area available for adsorption of Fluoride onto KSS samples decreases with the increase of particle size for the same dose of Fluoride, providing less active surface sites for adsorption.

Fig. 1.3: % Variation in fluoride concentration by different particle sizes (300 BSS, 200 BSS and 100 BSS) of Kota Stone Slurry (KSS)

X-Ray Diffraction Study of Kota Stone Slurry

Structure properties viz. crystal phase, crystallinity, crystallite size of raw Kota Stone Slurry, thermally activated KSS and adsorption catalyst are detected using power X-ray diffraction study. X-ray powder diffractometer (P analytical X' pert Pro) using Cu K α radiation, ($\lambda=1.54056\text{\AA}$) was used for determining crystal structure. The sample were scanned in 2θ range of $0-80^\circ$ at a scanning rate of $0.04^\circ \text{ s}^{-1}$. In XRD parallel planes are designated by their integers h, k, and l called miller indices, which are of reciprocals of the intersection between the lattice plane and the three crystallographic axis that span the unit cell of the crystal. A given set of planes with indices h, k, l cut the a-axis of the unit cell of h section, the b-axis in k sections and the c-axis in l sections. The incident X-ray beam and the lattice planes have to be oriented in a certain angle (θ) to allow diffraction.

Beams reflected at parallel lattice planes in the distance (d_{hkl}) interfere and give intensity maximum, which occurs as a peak in X-ray diffractogram, if their path difference $2d_{hkl}$ is an integer of wavelength (λ). This relationship can be expressed mathematically in Bragg's law [51, 52] as Equation 1.

$$n\lambda = 2d_{hkl} \sin \theta \quad [1]$$

The X-ray diffract gram consists of a plot of reflected intensity versus the diffracted angle 2θ . In powder samples with randomly oriented crystallites, the same amount of crystallites has the right orientation for the diffraction for all lattice planes[53].

If instead, a certain pattern is preferred the intensity of some reflection is lower or increased. Information about lattice parameters is available from peak position. The sharpness of diffraction lines is determined from their intensity together with their breadth, which is called the full width at half maximum(FWHM)[54].

The breadth of the peak is increase with decreasing crystalline size. The XRD patterns of a sample show the intensity of X-ray diffracted by different angles. The crystal phase identification is based on comparison of the set of reflections of the specimen with that of pure references phases or with database [55].

X-ray diffraction line broadening analysis is used to determine crystallite size of the crystalline phase using the Scherer formula [56 - 58] as in Equation 2.

$$\text{Crystallite Size} = \frac{K\lambda}{W \cos \theta} \quad [2]$$

Where, K = shape factor, λ = wavelength of X-ray radiation use, W = difference of broadened profile width of the experimental sample (W_b) and slandered profile width of the reference sample (W_s), and θ = angle of diffraction.

Fig. 1.4: X-Ray diffraction pattern of Kota stone slurry before fluoride adsorption – B.

Fig. 1.5: X-ray diffraction pattern of Kota stone slurry after fluoride adsorption -B1.

V COCLUSION

From above study it is clear that Kota stone slurry have best chemical composition. Each chemical compounds show good adsorption of fluoride. So, we can use Kota stone slurry as a cheapest adsorbent. The reduction in Fluoride adsorption capacity with increase in KSS samples size gives an idea about the porosity of adsorbent i.e., if the adsorbent is highly porous then it would not have significant effect on Fluoride adsorption at equilibrium. The

results obtained are in accordance with adsorption, where smaller particles of adsorbents the rate of fluoride uptake. The similar results were obtained in previous studies.

It is concluded that amount of Fluoride adsorption increases on decreasing particle size of Kota Stone Slurry from 300,200 and 100 BSS mesh. The relatively higher adsorption with smaller KSS particles is attributed to the fact that smaller particles yield large surface areas for adsorption of Fluoride. The larger particle size of KSS samples shows lesser Fluoride adsorption as compared to the smaller particle size of KSS samples.

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